

PROTOCOL

How to measure mental pain? A systematic review to identify all measurement instruments of mental pain and a comparison of their measurement properties.

Charvet C. ¹, Boutron I. ², Morvan Y. ³, Le Berre C. ³, Gaillard R. ^{2,4}, Fried E. ⁵, Chevance A. ³

¹ Sorbonne Université, F-75006 Paris

² Université de Paris, CRESS, INSERM, INRA, F-75004 Paris

³ Université de Nanterre

⁴ Centre Hospitalier Sainte-Anne, GHU Paris F-75014 Paris

⁵ Leyden University

Correspondance to:

Astrid Chevance, MD, PhD candidate

Hôpital Hôtel Dieu, Centre d'Épidémiologie Clinique, Paris, France

1 Place du Parvis Notre-Dame, Paris 75181, France

Tel: +33 6 79 77 95 24 email: astrid.chevance@clinicalepidemio.fr

Word count: 2827 words

Introduction

Mental pain, also referred to as “psychological pain”, “psychic pain” or “psychache” is an inner pain often compared to torture (1–4). It is different from both psychological ordeals (e.g. grief) and physical pain, although some neurological characteristics overlap (5,6). Mental pain is prevalent, and has been reported in a wide range of mental disorders, including depressive disorders, OCD, PTSD, and borderline personality disorder (4,7–9). Clinical research on mental pain has mainly focused on suicidal outcomes following Shneidman’s heritage, who concluded, after years of research on suicidal notes, that “without mental pain there is no suicide” (10). Mental pain is a risk factor for suicidal behavior (11) independently from depression (12) or hopelessness (13), and predicts self-harming behavior (14). Despite the importance of mental pain, it tends to be neglected in clinical practice and clinical research (15). For example, mental pain is neither part of the DSM-5 criteria for Major Depression, nor is it assessed as part of the most common rating scales for depression, but a recent large-scale study found that mental pain was reported as one of the most important outcomes by depressed patients (4,16),

Identifying a valid measurement instrument of mental pain is a first step to allow for adequate research and enhanced clinical practices. Narrative reviews have identified a range of instruments, but there is no consensus on what scales should be used in clinical research or practice (3,5,11). To our knowledge, there are no evaluations comparing the validity of scales for mental pain. Considering that it is common for measurement instrument of psychological dimension to lack of validity, it is plausible that mental pain scales also lack validity (17). As a consequence, if mental pain is assessed in daily care or clinical research at all, such measures may lack validity. Moreover, the lack of standardization in the use of mental pain measures prevents the comparison and combination of results (18,19). This goes back to the question on how mental pain is conceptualized theoretically, and whether theories of mental pain (and hence their operationalization) differ across scales (3).

The aim of this study is to identify, evaluate and compare measures of mental pain, with the goal to aid researchers and clinicians in selecting mental pain measures appropriate for their purposes.

Methods

We conducted a systematic review to identify all existing measurement instrument of mental pain and to assess the content validity and other measurement properties of the retrieved measurement instrument. We use the PRISMA checklist and the COSMIN (Consensus-based Standards for the selection of health Measurement Instruments) taxonomy and methodologies to design the study. (20–23)

Identification of the measurement instruments of mental pain

Sources Pubmed, Embase, PsychInfo and direct reach to MI's authors
Search strategy ("mental pain", "psychological pain", "psychache", "psychic pain")
Eligibility criteria Scientific publication mentioning the use of a MI to measure MP

Exclusion criteria

- Not about mental pain
- Animal studies
- Exclusive use of unstructured interviews
- No access to full text

Data extraction

- Characteristics of the study (year of publication, author, title, language)
- Aim of the studies (whether mental pain is the main outcome or not and whether the correlation between mental pain and suicide was investigated)
- Name of the MI used to measure MP
- Field of the studies (experimental psychology, clinical psychology, psychometric)
- Design (reviews, observational studies, experimental studies, development and validation studies)
- Population (type of mental disorder, sample size, countries)

The measurement instrument is rated sufficient, insufficient, inconsistent or indeterminate.

1. Eligibility criteria

We define a measurement instrument of mental pain as any standardized quantitative tool which claims to exclusively measure the construct of interest, ie mental pain, in any population.

To identify the measurement instrument of mental pain, we included scientific publications (e.g., clinical studies, comments, letter to editor, review in order not to miss any new measurement instrument available) mentioning a standardized measurement instrument of mental pain without restriction of date and languages and without restriction on the target population (age, gender, country). We excluded studies not involving humans, not using standardized measurement instrument of mental pain (such as unstructured interviews), and publications with no full text available. Finally, we excluded measurement instruments in which mental pain was measured as a subscale or via a few items among a larger set of items measuring other constructs.

2. Information sources and search strategy

We systematically searched three data bases relevant for psychiatry and psychological studies: PubMed, EMBASE and PsychINFO, from date of inception till the 22d of June 2020 with no language restriction. We searched the following synonyms of the construct “mental pain”, “psychological pain”, “psychache”, “psychic pain” (3,5,11). The full search equations are available in supplementary material. Management of the references was done with Endnote.

To ensure the comprehensive identification of the development and validation studies, we reached the authors of each measurement instrument asking them for any further information (published or unpublished manuscript or data) about the development and the validation of the measurement instrument.

3. Selection of the relevant scientific publications

Two investigators screened (either CC or CLB and AC) on title and abstract the articles independently, using the free systematic review web app Rayyan. Disagreements were resolved by consensus.

4. Data extraction process

All studies were examined in full text by one investigator (either CC or CLB) for identification of measurement instrument of mental pain. A second investigator randomly double checked the data extraction of 15% of the studies (AC).

5. Data items

The data charting form was designed using Excel and includes the information recommended by COSMIN. (24) We extracted:

- the name of the measurement instrument,
- the characteristics of the study (e.g., journal, year of publication, author, title, country, language).
- the field of study
 - psychology : studying experience and human behavior
 - experimental psychology : involving an experimental setting
 - social psychology : focusing on social interaction
 - psychometric : focusing on the development or validation of a standardized measurement instrument or on the measurement of a construct
 - biomarker study : studying the correlation with a physiological parameter
 - effectiveness research : testing or involving a therapeutic method
- the population
 - sample size
 - type:
 - General population
 - patients
 - type of disorder :
 - mood disorder,
 - schizophrenia,
 - anxiety disorder,
 - addiction,
 - abuse/trauma,
 - personality disorder
- The design of the study

- reviews,
- observational studies,
- experimental studies,
- development and validation studies),
- Whether mental pain is the main outcome or not
- Whether the correlation between mental pain and suicide was investigated or not, so as to evaluate the interest for mental pain in its traditional context (suicide studies), and in other context of mental health.

The data chart form is available in supplementary material 2.

6. Analysis and synthesis of results

a) Identification of measurement instrument of mental pain

The list of all identified measurement instrument is presented in a table reporting their name, the seminal paper (author, date), a description of the tool (number of items, patient-reported outcome), the context of use, the target population, the number of studies using it, their field, design, aims, and the population investigated by the studies using it (appendix 1). We will describe and compare the content of the different instrument using a circular representation such as in Fried 2016 (16). Two researchers (CC and AC) will classify each item of each scale using semantic and clinical knowledge in different inductively defined categories.

b) Assessment of the validity of the measurement instruments of mental pain

For each measurement instrument, we identified among the previous included studies all development and validation articles (e.g. all papers investigating the measurement properties of one given measurement instrument) (24) We excluded studies in which the measurement instrument is used as an external validator for another instrument.

Three investigators (CC AC and YM) extracted and rated independently the data about the development, the content validity and the other measurement properties if relevant. CC is a psychiatrist, AC is a psychiatrist with expertise in clinical epidemiology, COS development and qualitative research, YM is a psychologist with expertise on psychometrics. Disagreements were resolved by consensus with experts (EF and RG). The reviewers report no conflict of interest with any of the measurement instruments.

We evaluated the quality of the development using COSMIN box 1 and table 1 and algorithm 1 (appendix 2). Each of the 35 aspects is rated very good, adequate, doubtful, inadequate or not applicable. The overall rating is described in algorithm 1 appendix 2

Assessment of content validity of the measurement instrument

Content validity is the degree to which the content of an instrument is an adequate reflection of the construct to be measured. (25) Three aspects of content validity are being distinguished: (1) relevance (all aspects should be relevant for the construct of interest within a specific population and context of use), (2) comprehensiveness (no key aspects of the construct should be missing), and (3) comprehensibility (the aspects should be understood by patients as intended). (25,26)

As recommended by COSMIN, we evaluated the quality of the content validity studies using COSMIN box 2, and table 2 and algorithm 2 (appendix 3), and the content validity, using the criteria for content validity table (appendix 4). The overall rating is obtained by taking the lowest rating of any standards in box 2.

As content validity is considered to be the most important measurement property by experts of COSMIN, we will use a filter approach and assessed the remaining measurement properties only if the content validity was rated sufficient or inconsistent.

Assessment of the other measurement properties

As recommended, we will rate the quality of the studies regarding structural validity (box 3), internal consistency (box 4), cross-cultural validity, measurement invariance (box 5), reliability (box 6), measurement error (box 7), criterion validity (box 8), hypotheses testing for construct validity (box 9), responsiveness (box 10) (for boxes 3-10, see appendix 5). The measurement properties of the measurement instrument will be rated using the criteria for other measurement properties of COSMIN (appendix 6).

The final rating of all measurement properties (content validity + others) of each measurement instrument will be presented in COSMIN table 3 (appendix 7)

Expected results

- Identification of all existing measurement instrument for mental pain
- Evaluation of the content validity of all measurement instruments

- Evaluation of the other measurement properties for measurement instruments with sufficient or inconsistent content validity
- Rating of the evidence quality of each measurement instrument

Perspectives

- This study will help improving the current measurement instrument for mental pain or the development of new measurement instrument for mental pain
- This study will help clinicians and researchers to choose measurement instrument
- This study will help for the development of core outcome sets

Bibliography

1. Orbach I, Mikulincer M, Sirota P, Gilboa-Schechtman E. Mental pain: a multidimensional operationalization and definition. *Suicide Life Threat Behav.* 2003;33(3):219–30.
2. Orbach I, Mikulincer M, Gilboa-Schechtman E, Sirota P. Mental Pain and Its Relationship to Suicidality and Life Meaning. *Suicide Life Threat Behav.* 2003 Feb 1;33:231–41.
3. Tossani E. The concept of mental pain. *Psychother Psychosom.* 2013;82(2):67–73.
4. Chevance A, Ravaud P, Tomlinson A, Berre CL, Teufer B, Touboul S, et al. Identifying outcomes for depression that matter to patients, informal caregivers, and health-care professionals: qualitative content analysis of a large international online survey. *Lancet Psychiatry.* 2020 Aug 1;7(8):692–702.
5. Mee S, Bunney BG, Reist C, Potkin SG, Bunney WE. Psychological pain: a review of evidence. *J Psychiatr Res.* 2006 Dec;40(8):680–90.
6. Conejero I, Olié E, Calati R, Ducasse D, Courtet P. Psychological Pain, Depression, and Suicide: Recent Evidences and Future Directions. *Curr Psychiatry Rep.* 2018 05;20(5):33.
7. Zanarini MC, Frankenburg FR, DeLuca CJ, Hennen J, Khera GS, Gunderson JG. The pain of being borderline: dysphoric states specific to borderline personality disorder. *Harv Rev Psychiatry.* 1998 Dec;6(4):201–7.
8. Demirkol ME, Namlı Z, Eriş Davul Ö, Karaytuğ MO, Tamam L, Yılmaz H. Psychache and Suicidal History in Patients with Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder. *Neuropsychiatr Dis Treat.* 2019 Dec 24;15:3531–9.
9. Monson CM, Price JL, Rodriguez BF, Ripley MP, Warner RA. Emotional deficits in military-related PTSD: An investigation of content and process disturbances. *J Trauma Stress.* 2004;17(3):275–9.
10. Shneidman ES. *The Suicidal Mind.* Oxford University Press; 1998. 212 p.
11. Verrocchio MC, Carrozzino D, Marchetti D, Andreasson K, Fulcheri M, Bech P. Mental Pain and Suicide: A Systematic Review of the Literature. *Front Psychiatry [Internet].* 2016 Jun 20 [cited 2020 May 31];7. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4913233/>
12. Soumani A, Damigos D, Oulis P, Masdrakis V, Ploumpidis D, Mavreas V, et al. Mental pain and suicide risk: application of the Greek version of the Mental Pain and the Tolerance of Mental Pain scale. *Psychiatr Psychiatr.* 2011 Dec;22(4):330–40.
13. Troister T, Davis MP, Lowndes A, Holden RR. A five-month longitudinal study of psychache and suicide ideation: replication in general and high-risk university students. *Suicide Life Threat Behav.* 2013 Dec;43(6):611–20.

14. Korner A, Gerull F, Stevenson J, Mearns R. Harm avoidance, self-harm, psychic pain, and the borderline personality: life in a “haunted house.” *Compr Psychiatry*. 2007 Jun;48(3):303–8.
15. Sensky T. Suffering. *Int J Integr Care*. 2010 Jan 29;10 Suppl:e024.
16. Fried EI. The 52 symptoms of major depression: Lack of content overlap among seven common depression scales. *J Affect Disord*. 2017 Jan 15;208:191–7.
17. Flake JK, Fried EI. Measurement Schmeasurement: Questionable Measurement Practices and How to Avoid Them. *Adv Methods Pract Psychol Sci*. 2020 Dec 1;3(4):456–65.
18. Chalmers I, Bracken MB, Djulbegovic B, Garattini S, Grant J, Gülmezoglu AM, et al. How to increase value and reduce waste when research priorities are set. *The Lancet*. 2014 Jan 11;383(9912):156–65.
19. Williamson P, Altman D, Blazeby J, Clarke M, Gargon E. Driving up the quality and relevance of research through the use of agreed core outcomes. *J Health Serv Res Policy*. 2012 Jan;17(1):1–2.
20. Moher D, Liberati A, Tetzlaff J, Altman DG, PRISMA Group. Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the PRISMA statement. *PLoS Med*. 2009 Jul 21;6(7):e1000097.
21. Mokkink LB, de Vet HCW, Prinsen C a. C, Patrick DL, Alonso J, Bouter LM, et al. COSMIN Risk of Bias checklist for systematic reviews of Patient-Reported Outcome Measures. *Qual Life Res Int J Qual Life Asp Treat Care Rehabil*. 2018;27(5):1171–9.
22. Mokkink, L.B, Prinsen, C. a. C, Patrick, D.L, Alonso, J., Bouter, L. M, de Vet, H. C. W, et al. COSMIN methodology for systematic reviews of Patient-Reported Outcome Measures (PROMs). User manual.
23. Terwee CB, Prinsen C a. C, Chiarotto A, Westerman MJ, Patrick DL, Alonso J, et al. COSMIN methodology for evaluating the content validity of patient-reported outcome measures: a Delphi study. *Qual Life Res Int J Qual Life Asp Treat Care Rehabil*. 2018;27(5):1159–70.
24. Prinsen C a. C, Mokkink LB, Bouter LM, Alonso J, Patrick DL, de Vet HCW, et al. COSMIN guideline for systematic reviews of patient-reported outcome measures. *Qual Life Res Int J Qual Life Asp Treat Care Rehabil*. 2018;27(5):1147–57.
25. Mokkink L, Terwee C, Knol D, Stratford P, Alonso J, Patrick D, et al. The COSMIN checklist for evaluating the methodological quality of studies on measurement properties: A clarification of its content. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2010 Mar 1;10:22.
26. Terwee, C. B, Prinsen, C. a. C, Chiarotto, A., de Vet, H. C. W, Bouter, L. M, Alonso, J., et al. COSMIN methodology for assessing the content validity of PROMs. User manual. version 1.0.

Appendix 1

MI	Seminal paper	Date	PRO	Number of item	Initial context of use and/or target population	N° of studies	Field	Design	Aim	Study population
XXX										

Appendix 2

COSMIN box 1. Standards for evaluating the quality of the development

Ratings: V= very good; A = adequate; D = doubtful; I = inadequate; N= not applicable

	MI		
	ref		
1a. Design			
<i>General design requirements</i>	Rater 1	Rater 2	Consensus
1 Is a clear description provided of the construct to be measured?			
2 Is the origin of the construct clear: was a theory, conceptual framework or disease model used or clear rationale provided to define the construct to be measured?			
3 Is a clear description provided of the target population for which the PROM was developed?			
4 Is a clear description provided of the context of use (i.e. discriminative, evaluative purpose, and/or predictive)			
5 Was the development study performed in a sample representing the target population for which the was developed?			
<i>Concept elicitation (relevance and comprehensiveness)</i>	Rater 1	Rater 2	Consensus
6 Was an appropriate qualitative data collection method used to identify relevant items for a new MI?			
7 Were skilled group moderators/ interviewers used?			

8	Were the group meetings or interviews based on an appropriate topic or interview guide?			
9	Were the group meetings or interviews recorded and transcribed verbatim?			
10	Was an appropriate approach used to analyse the data?			
11	Was at least part of the data coded independently?			
12	Was data collection continued until saturation was reached?			
13	For quantitative studies: was the sample size appropriate?			
SUBTOTAL QUALITY CONCEPT ELICITATION STUDY <i>Lowest score of items 6-13</i>				
TOTAL QUALITY OF THE DESIGN <i>Lowest score of items 1-13</i>				

1b. Cognitive interview study or other pilot test

Was a cognitive interview study or other pilot test performed? <i>If NO skip items</i>		Rater 1	Rater 2	Consensus
14	15-35			
<i>General design requirements</i>		Rater 1	Rater 2	Consensus
15	Was the cognitive interview study or other pilot test performed in a sample representing the target population?			
<i>Comprehensibility</i>		Rater 1	Rater 2	Consensus
16	Were patients asked about the <u>comprehensibility</u> of the MI? <i>If NO or not clear, skip items 17-25</i>			
17	Were all items tested in their final form?	Rater 1	Rater 2	Consensus
18	Was an appropriate qualitative method used to assess the <u>comprehensibility</u> of the PROM instructions, items, response options, and recall period?			
19	Was each item tested in an appropriate number of patients?			
20	Were skilled interviewers used?			

21	Were the interviews based on an appropriate interview guide?			
22	Were the interviews recorded and transcribed verbatim?			
23	Was an appropriate approach used to analyse the data?			
24	Were at least two researchers involved in the analysis?			
25	Were problems regarding the comprehensibility of the PROM instructions, items, response options, and recall period appropriately addressed by adapting the PROM?			
SUBTOTAL QUALITY OF COMPREHENSIBILITY STUDY <i>Lowest score of items 15-25</i>				
Comprehensiveness		Rater 1	Rater 2	Consensus
Were patients asked about the <u>comprehensiveness</u> of the MI? <i>If NO or not clear, skip items 27-35</i>				
26	Was the final set of items tested?	Rater 1	Rater 2	Consensus
27	Was an appropriate method used for assessing the comprehensiveness of the PROM?			
28	Was each item tested in an appropriate number of patients?			
29	Were skilled interviewers used?			
30	Were the interviews based on an appropriate interview guide?			
31	Were the interviews recorded and transcribed verbatim?			
32	Was an appropriate approach used to analyse the data?			
33	Were at least two researchers involved in the analysis?			
34	Were problems regarding the <u>comprehensiveness</u> of the PROM appropriately addressed by adapting the MI?			
35	SUBTOTAL QUALITY OF COMPREHENSIVENESS STUDY <i>Lowest score of items 15, 26-35</i>			
TOTAL QUALITY OF THE PILOT STUDY <i>Lowest score of items 14-35</i>				

TOTAL QUALITY OF THE PROM DEVELOPMENT STUDY <i>Lowest score of items 1-35</i>			
--	--	--	--

Table 1. Quality of the development

PROM	PROM design						Cognitive interview (CI) study ²				TOTAL PROM DEVELOPMENT	
	General design requirements					Concept elicitation ¹	Total PROM design	General design requirements	Comprehensibility	Comprehensiveness		Total CI study
	Clear construct	Clear origin of construct	Clear target population for which the PROM was developed	Clear context of use	PROM developed in sample representing the target population						CI study performed in sample representing the target population	
#VALEUR!	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Appendix 3

COSMIN box 2. Standards for evaluating the quality of content validity studies

Score: V= very good; A = adequate; D = doubtful; I = inadequate; N= not applicable

		PROM		
		ref		
		rater	rater	
		1	2	Consensus
2a. Asking patient about relevance				
1	Was an appropriate method used to ask patients whether each item is <u>relevant</u> for their experience with the condition?			
2	Was each item tested in an appropriate number of patients?			
3	Were skilled group moderators/interviewers used?			
4	Were the group meetings or interviews based on an appropriate topic or interview guide?			
5	Were the group meetings or interviews recorded and transcribed verbatim?			
6	Was an appropriate approach used to analyse the data?			
7	Were at least two researchers involved in the analysis?			
SUBTOTAL QUALITY OF RELEVANCE STUDY <i>Lowest score of items 1-7</i>				
		rater	rater	
		1	2	Consensus
2b. Asking patients about comprehensiveness				
8	Was an appropriate method used for assessing the <u>comprehensiveness</u> of the PROM?			
9	Was each item tested in an appropriate number of patients?			
10	Were skilled group moderators/interviewers used?			
11	Were the group meetings or interviews based on an appropriate topic or interview guide?			
12	Were the group meetings or interviews recorded and transcribed verbatim?			

13 Was an appropriate approach used to analyse the data?			
14 Were at least two researchers involved in the analysis?			
SUBTOTAL QUALITY OF COMPREHENSIVENESS STUDY <i>Lowest score of items 8-14</i>			

2c. Asking patients about comprehensibility	rater 1	rater 2	Consensus
15 Was an appropriate qualitative method used for assessing the <u>comprehensibility</u> of the PROM instructions, items, response options, and recall period?			
16 Was each item tested in an appropriate number of patients?			
17 Were skilled group moderators/interviewers used?			
18 Were the group meetings or interviews based on an appropriate topic or interview guide?			
19 Were the group meetings or interviews recorded and transcribed verbatim?			
20 Was an appropriate approach used to analyse the data?			
21 Were at least two researchers involved in the analysis?			
SUBTOTAL QUALITY OF COMPREHENSIBILITY STUDY <i>Lowest score of items 15-21</i>			

2d. Asking professionals about relevance	rater 1	rater 2	Consensus
22 Was an appropriate method used to ask professionals whether each item is <u>relevant</u> for the construct of interest?			
23 Were professionals from all relevant disciplines included?			
24 Was each item tested in an appropriate number of professionals?			
25 Was an appropriate approach used to analyse the data?			
26 Were at least two researchers involved in the analysis?			
SUBTOTAL QUALITY OF RELEVANCE STUDY <i>Lowest score of items 22-26</i>			

2e. Asking professionals about comprehensiveness	rater 1	rater 2	Consensus
27 Was an appropriate method used for assessing the <u>comprehensiveness</u> of the PROM?			
28 Were professionals from all relevant disciplines included?			

29	Was each item tested in an appropriate number of professionals?			
30	Was an appropriate approach used to analyse the data?			
31	Were at least two researchers involved in the analysis?			
SUBTOTAL QUALITY OF COMPREHENSIVENESS STUDY <i>Lowest score of items 27-31</i>				

Table 2 Quality of studies on measurement properties

PRO M	Content validity					Struc tural validi ty	Intern al consis tency	Cro ss- cult ural vali dity	Relia bility	Measur ement error	Crite rion validi ty	Construct validity		Responsiveness			
	Asking patients			Asking experts								Conve rgent validit y	Kn wn gro ups vali dity	Comp arison with gold stand ard	Comp arison with other instru ments	Comp arison betwe en subgr oups	Comp arison before and after interv ention
	Relev ance	Compr e- hensiv eness	Comp re- hensi bility	Relev ance	Compr e- hensiv eness												
#VAL EUR!	0	0	0	0	0	v	v	v	v	v	v	v	v	v	v	v	v

Appendix 4

COSMIN Criteria for content validity

	PROM development study	PROM development study	PROM development study	Content validity study 1	Content validity study 1	Content validity study 1	Content validity study 2 ²	Content validity study 2 ²	Content validity study 2 ²	Rating of reviewers	Rating of reviewers	Rating of reviewers	OVERALL RATING PROM ³	OVERALL RATING PROM ³	OVERALL RATING PROM ³	QUALITY OF EVIDENCE	QUALITY OF EVIDENCE	QUALITY OF EVIDENCE
PROM (subscale)	+/-/?	+/-/?	+/-/?	+/-/?	+/-/?	+/-/?	+/-/?	+/-/?	+/-/?	+/-/?	+/-/?	+/-/?	+/-/?	+/-/?	+/-/?	High, moderate, low, very low	High, moderate, low, very low	High, moderate, low, very low
	rater 1	rater 2	consensus	rater 1	rater 2	consensus	rater 1	rater 2	consensus	rater 1	rater 2	consensus	rater 1	rater 2	consensus	rater 1	rater 2	consensus
Relevance																		
1 Are the included items relevant for the construct of interest? ¹																		
2 Are the included items relevant for the target population of interest? ¹																		
3 Are the included items relevant for the context of use of interest? ¹																		
4 Are the response options appropriate?																		
5 Is the recall period appropriate?																		
RELEVANCE RATING (+ / - / ± / ?)																		

Comprehensiveness																				
6	Are all key concepts included?																			
COMPREHENSIVENESS RATING (+ / - / ± / ?)																				
Comprehensibility																				
7	Are the PROM instructions understood by the population of interest as intended?																			
8	Are the PROM items and response options understood by the population of interest as intended?																			
9	Are the PROM items appropriately worded?																			
1	Do the response options match the question?																			
0																				
COMPREHENSIBILITY RATING (+ / - / ± / ?)																				
CONTENT VALIDITY RATING (+ / - / ± / ?)																				

¹ These criteria refer to the construct, population, and context of use of interest in the systematic review.

² Add more columns if more content validity studies are available

³ If ratings are inconsistent between studies, consider using separate tables for subgroups of studies with consistent results.

Appendix 5

Evaluation of the quality of the measurement properties studies

Only those parts of the boxes need to be completed for which information is available

Score: V= very good; A = adequate; D = doubtful; I = inadequate; N= not applicable

Article reference:		Measurement instrument		
		ref		
3. Structural validity		rate 1	rate 2	Consensus
	unidimensionality or structural validity?			
1	For CTT: Was exploratory or confirmatory factor analysis performed?			
2	For IRT/Rasch: does the chosen model fit to the research question?			
3	Was the sample size included in the analysis adequate?			
4	Were there any other important flaws?			
TOTAL <i>Lowest score of items 1-4</i>				V
4. Internal consistency		rate 1	rate 2	Consensus

1	Was an internal consistency statistic calculated for each unidimensional (sub)scale separately?			
2	For continuous scores: Was Cronbach's alpha or omega calculated?			
3	For dichotomous scores: Was Cronbach's alpha or KR-20 calculated?			
4	For IRT-based scores: Was standard error of the theta (SE (θ)) or reliability coefficient of estimated latent trait value (index of (subject or item) separation) calculated?			
5	Were there any other important flaws?			
TOTAL Lowest score of items 1-5				v

5. Cross-cultural validity\measurement invariance		ra te r 1	ra te r 2	Cons ensu s
1	Were the samples similar for relevant characteristics except for the group variable?			
2	Was an adequate approach used to analyse the data?			
3	Was the sample size included in the analysis adequate?			
4	Were there any other important flaws?			
TOTAL Lowest score of items 1-4				v

6. Reliability		ra te r 1	ra te r 2	Cons ensu s
1	Were patients stable in the interim period on the construct to be measured?			
2	Was the time interval appropriate?			
3	Were the test conditions similar for the measurements? e.g. type of administration, environment, instructions			
4	For continuous scores: Was an intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) calculated?			
5	For dichotomous/nominal/ordinal scores: Was kappa calculated?			
6	For ordinal scores: Was a weighted kappa calculated?			

7	For ordinal scores: Was the weighting scheme described? e.g. linear, quadratic			
8	Were there any other important flaws?			
TOTAL <i>Lowest score of items 1-8</i>				v

7. Measurement error		ra te r 1	ra te r 2	Cons ensu s
1	Were patients stable in the interim period on the construct to be measured?			
2	Was the time interval appropriate?			
3	Were the test conditions similar for the measurements? e.g. type of administration, environment, instructions			
4	For continuous scores: Was the Standard Error of Measurement (SEM), Smallest Detectable Change (SDC) or Limits of Agreement (LoA) calculated?			
5	For dichotomous/nominal/ordinal scores: Was the percentage (positive and negative) agreement calculated?			
6	Were there any other important flaws?			
TOTAL <i>Lowest score of items 1-6</i>				v

8. Criterion validity		ra te r 1	ra te r 2	Cons ensu s
1	For continuous scores: Were correlations, or the area under the receiver operating curve calculated?			
2	For dichotomous scores: Were sensitivity and specificity determined?			
3	Were there any other important flaws?			
TOTAL <i>Lowest score of items 1-3</i>				v

9. Hypotheses testing for construct validity

9a. Comparison with other outcome measurement instruments (convergent validity)

		ra te r 1	ra te r 2	Cons ensu s
1	Is it clear what the comparator instrument(s) measure(s)?			
2	Were the measurement properties of the comparator instrument(s) adequate?			
3	Was the statistical method appropriate for the hypotheses to be tested?			
4	Were there any other important flaws?			
TOTAL <i>Lowest score of items 1-4</i>				v

9b. Comparison between subgroups (discriminative or known-groups validity)

		ra te r 1	ra te r 2	Cons ensu s
5	Was an adequate description provided of important characteristics of the subgroups?			
6	Was the statistical method appropriate for the hypotheses to be tested?			
7	Were there any other important flaws?			
TOTAL <i>Lowest score of items 5-7</i>				v

10. Responsiveness

10a. Criterion approach (i.e. comparison to a gold standard)

		ra te r 1	ra te r 2	Cons ensu s
1	For continuous scores: Were correlations between change scores, or the area under the Receiver Operator Curve (ROC) curve calculated?			
2	For dichotomous scales: Were sensitivity and specificity (changed versus not changed) determined?			
3	Were there any other important flaws?			

		TOTAL <i>Lowest score of items 1-3</i>			v
10b. Construct approach (i.e. hypotheses testing; comparison with other outcome measurement instruments)					
			ra	ra	Cons
			te	te	ensu
			r	r	s
			1	2	
4	Is it clear what the comparator instrument(s) measure(s)?				
5	Were the measurement properties of the comparator instrument(s) adequate?				
6	Was the statistical method appropriate for the hypotheses to be tested?				
7	Were there any other important flaws?				
		TOTAL <i>Lowest score of items 4-7</i>			v
10c. Construct approach: (i.e. hypotheses testing: comparison between subgroups)					
			ra	ra	Cons
			te	te	ensu
			r	r	s
			1	2	
8	Was an adequate description provided of important characteristics of the subgroups?				
9	Was the statistical method appropriate for the hypotheses to be tested?				
10	Were there any other important flaws?				
		TOTAL <i>Lowest score of items 8-10</i>			v
10d. Construct approach: (i.e. hypotheses testing: before and after intervention)					
			ra	ra	Cons
			te	te	ensu
			r	r	s
			1	2	
11	Was an adequate description provided of the intervention given?				
12	Was the statistical method appropriate for the hypotheses to be tested?				
13	Were there any other important flaws?				
		TOTAL <i>Lowest score of items 11-13</i>			v